

Synthesis of Unsymmetric *Bis*-Coumarinoxy-Alkanes

K. A. THAKAR*, (Mrs.) R. V. PATHAK and (Miss) ACHLA B. DUMIR

Chemistry Department, Marathwada University, Aurangabad-431 004

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Several unsymmetric *bis*-coumarinoxy alkanes have been synthesised by the condensation of α -coumarinoxy- ω -bromo alkanes with variously substituted hydroxy coumarins in the presence of acetone and potassium carbonate.

COUMARINS are known to possess antifungal and antibacterial properties¹⁻³. Disodium cromoglycate (DSCG) which was prepared by Cairns *et al*⁴ is known to possess antiasthmatic properties. Some symmetric *bis*-coumarinoxy alkanes which were prepared by us⁵ are found to possess anti-allergic activity⁶. Taking into account the general activities of coumarins, DSCG and sym. *bis*-coumarinoxy alkanes it was thought that the unsym. *bis*-coumarinoxy alkanes may possess interesting physiological activity. With this in view the synthesis of unsym. *bis*-coumarinoxy alkanes was carried out.

We have synthesised several unsym. *bis*-coumarinoxy alkanes taking into account the parameters like (i) substituents in the benzenoid part, (ii) substituents in the α -pyrone ring, (iii) the length of the alkane chain and (iv) the position of the attachment of ether linkage to benzene ring.

Hydroxy coumarins, the starting materials for the preparation of unsym. *bis*-coumarinoxy alkanes, were prepared by the known methods⁷. One mole of hydroxy coumarin when refluxed with one mole of dihaloalkane in the presence of potassium carbonate and dry acetone gave a mixture of α -coumarinoxy- ω -bromoalkane(I) and sym. *bis*-coumarinoxy alkane⁸. These compounds were separated by extraction with ether, since α -coumarinoxy- ω -bromoalkane is soluble in ether and *bis*-coumarinoxy alkane is insoluble in ether. The physical data of α -coumarinoxy- ω -bromoalkanes used in this work is given in Table 1.

These α -coumarinoxy- ω -bromoalkanes were condensed with variously substituted hydroxy coumarins to get unsym. *bis*-coumarinoxy alkanes (II-VII). The physical data of these compounds is represented in Table 2.

Infrared: IR spectra (Nujol) of unsymmetric compounds showed bands around 1720, 1630 and 1270 cm^{-1} characteristic of C=O of coumarins, C=C and asymmetric stretch of ether linkage respectively.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF α -COUMARINOXY- ω -BROMOALKANES(I)

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	n	Linkage	M.P.°C
1.	H	H	—	2	7'	112-13 ^b
2.	H	H	—	3	7'	83 ^b
3.	H	H	—	4	7'	66 ^a
4.	H	H	—	5	7'	60 ^c
5.	H	—	H	2	6'	109 ^a
6.	H	—	H	3	6'	85-86 ^b
7.	—	H	CH ₃	4	5'	119-20 ^b

All compounds were obtained in 30-40% yield and gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

a=crystallised from methanol,

b=crystallised from ethanol,

c=crystallised from petroleum ether.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF UNSYMMETRIC *Bis*-COUMARINOXY ALKANES (II-VII)

II

III

* Address for correspondence.

(Table 2 Contd.)

IV

V

VI

VII

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	n	M.P. °C
Compound II							
1.	H	CH ₃	H	C ₂ H ₅	H	2	223 ^b
2.	H	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃	2	240 ^a
3.	Cl	CH ₃	H	H	H	2	241-42 ^a
4.	H	H	CH ₃	H	H	2	231 ^a
5.	H	CH ₂ COOCH ₃	H	H	H	2	193-95 ^a
6.	H	CH ₃	H	C ₂ H ₅	H	3	175-76 ^b
7.	H	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃	3	223-24 ^a
8.	Cl	CH ₃	H	H	H	3	220 ^a
9.	H	H	CH ₃	H	H	3	168-69 ^b
10.	H	CH ₂ COOCH ₃	H	H	H	3	192-93 ^a
11.	H	CH ₃	H	C ₂ H ₅	H	4	160-61 ^b
12.	H	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃	4	197-99 ^a
13.	Cl	CH ₃	H	H	H	4	155 ^b
14.	H	H	CH ₃	H	H	4	180 ^b
15.	H	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃	5	146-47 ^b
16.	Cl	CH ₃	H	H	H	5	164-65 ^a

Compound III							
17.	—	—	—	—	—	2	214-15 ^a
18.	—	—	—	—	—	3	190 ^b
19.	—	—	—	—	—	4	122-23 ^c
20.	—	—	—	—	—	5	168-70 ^a
Compound IV							
21.	—	—	—	—	—	2	252-53 ^a
22.	—	—	—	—	—	3	194-95 ^a
23.	—	—	—	—	—	4	222-24 ^a
24.	—	—	—	—	—	5	195 ^a
Compound V							
25.	H	CH ₃	H	C ₂ H ₅	H	2	167-68 ^b
26.	H	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃	2	225-26 ^a
27.	Cl	CH ₃	H	H	H	2	227 ^a
28.	H	H	CH ₃	H	H	2	210 ^a
29.	H	CH ₂ COOCH ₃	H	H	H	2	183-84 ^b
30.	H	CH ₃	H	C ₂ H ₅	H	3	197-98 ^a
31.	H	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃	3	194-95 ^b
32.	Cl	CH ₃	H	H	H	3	214-15 ^a
33.	H	H	CH ₃	H	H	3	192-93 ^a
34.	H	CH ₂ COOCH ₃	H	H	H	3	165-66 ^b
Compound VI							
35.	—	—	—	—	—	2	220 ^a
36.	—	—	—	—	—	3	238-3. ^a
Compound VII							
37.	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃	—	4	241-42 ^a
38.	CH ₃	H	C ₂ H ₅	H	—	4	215 ^a
39.	H	CH ₃	H	H	—	4	175 ^b

All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

a=crystallised from acetic acid,

b=crystallised from 80% acetic acid,

c=crystallised from 60% acetic acid.

Experimental

General procedure for the preparation of—

(i) α -Coumarinoxy- ω -bromoalkanes: A mixture of hydroxy coumarin (0.1 mole), dibromoalkane (0.1 mole), anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.2 mole) and dry acetone was refluxed for 8-10 hrs. Acetone was distilled off and residue was poured over ice water. The solid obtained after filtration was washed with a dilute solution of sodium hydroxide and extracted with ether. α -Coumarinoxy- ω -bromoalkane was obtained by the evaporation of ether. Yield: 30-40%.

(ii) *Unsymmetric bis-coumarinoxy alkanes*: α -Coumarinoxy- ω -bromoalkane (0.01 mole) was refluxed with hydroxy coumarin (0.01 mole) in the presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ (0.02 mole) and acetone for 13-14 hrs. The solid obtained after the distillation of acetone was poured over ice and water. The solid obtained after the filtration was washed with a dilute solution of sodium hydroxide. This solid was finally washed with ether to remove excess α -coumarinoxy- ω -bromoalkane. The products were crystallised from the proper solvents. Yield: 70-80%.

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